

Research Article

High Performance Liquid Chromatography Assay with UV Detection for the Determination of Ciprofloxacin in Human Plasma

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ABSTRACT

Accurate, sensitive and specific isocratic High Performance Liquid Chromatography method with UV detection was developed, validated and applied for the determination of Ciprofloxacin in human plasma. Sample preparation was carried out with the addition of an internal standard Gatifluoxacin to plasma samples followed by a liquid-liquid extraction using perchloric acid. Separation was achieved with Waters symmetry C18, 5 μ m, 150 x 3.9 mm column using a mixture of potassium phosphate buffer (pH =3.1) : acetonitrile : methanol (72:12:16, v:v:v) in addition to tetrabutyleammonium hydroxide as an ion pair reagent. The calibration curve for Ciprofloxacin in plasma was linear in the range 0.5-10 μ g/mL with $r^2 = 0.9998$. The lower limit of quantitation (LLOQ) and limit of detection (LOD) for Ciprofloxacin in plasma were respectively 0.032 μ g/mL and 0.0090 μ g/mL.

Inter and intra-day precessions in the measurements of three different levels QC samples in human plasma were in the range 0.85-2.47%, 0.14-0.24% and 0.10-0.35% respectively.

Method recovery, short-and long term stabilities were within the acceptable values. The developed method of analysis provided a sensitive and specific assay for Ciprofloxacin and was found to be suitable for the analysis of the drug in human plasma.

Keywords: Ciprofloxacin , HPLC, human plasma.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ciprofloxacin are broad-spectrum antibiotics with concentration dependent bactericidal activity. It is well absorbed after oral administration and is widely distributed throughout the body. Like other fluoroquinolones, it is both metabolized and excreted unchanged in the urine (Molinaro et al. 1997). A number of Ciprofloxacin pharmacokinetic studies conducted in adults, including patients with cystic fibrosis. These studies have provided consistent results, with an average volume of distribution of 2 to 3 l/kg and an elimination half-life of 4 to 5 hours (Jacobs M, 1997). Patients with cystic fibrosis are not found to differ in their drug elimination compared to matched controls (Jacobs M, 1997). Following oral administration of a 500 mg tablet, maximum peak serum concentrations ranging from 1.5 to 2.9 mg/l are achieved within 1–2 h of dosing. Area values under the serum concentration curve (AUC) range from 6.8 to 12.7 mg·h/l with an elimination half-life ranging from approximately 3 h to 5 h (Mandell and Pertri 1996). Generally, Ciprofloxacin tablets dissolve rapidly in the gastrointestinal tract and are absorbed in the duodenum and jejunum. Following oral dosing, the bioavailability of Ciprofloxacin is between 70% and 80%. Concomitant administration of the oral tablet with food is reported to result in a prolonged time to reach peak serum levels, although overall bioavailability does not appear to be significantly altered (Perez-Trallero et al. 1998 and Klustersky et al. 1974). Various HPLC methods with UV, fluorescence or mass spectrometry detection have been reported in the literature for the determination quinolones including Ciprofloxacin in human plasma and other biological fluids. Some of these methods involve the use ion-pair reagent to get a better peak shape (Manceau et al 1999 ; Zahi et al 1995 ; Al-Dgither et al 2006 and Krol et al 1995). An HPLC method developed for the determination of Ciprofloxacin and three of its metabolites in urine, serum and plasma based on flurometric detection after post column induction (Sundeland et al 2004). The approach is found to enhance the sensitivity of Ciprofloxacin metabolites by up to 44 times that other –wise have very weak natural fluorescence. HPLC analysis of Ciprofloxacin in plasma after protein precipitation is reported for 5 different oral formulations (Maya et al 2001). Analysis of levofloxacin and Ciprofloxacin in plasma and microdialysates using HPLC in isocratic mode is also

reported. Plasma proteins are precipitated using methanol (Neckel et al 2002). HPLC with direct injection of plasma and Mueller-Hinton broth for the analysis of Ciprofloxacin is also reported (Ba et al 1998). This approach required the use of a pre-column to trap the sample and then switch into an analytical column to separate Ciprofloxacin. The work of Gonzalez et al. involve the separation of five fluoroquinolones using HPLC with fluorometric detection (Gonzalez et al 2006). Their work is the first report of the analysis of the five fluoroquinolones in equine endometrial tissues. The effect of different separation parameters such as ion-pair, competing base reagent, buffer, pH and organic modifier on HPLC separation of Ciprofloxacin and four more fluoroquinolones in human plasma is investigated (Liang et al 2002). The current study was devised to develop and validate a liquid chromatographic (HPLC) method for Ciprofloxacin determination in human plasma as a precursor for pharmacokinetic study of Ciprofloxacin. To support clinical studies, the method was proved to be a feasible analytical tool to quantitate Ciprofloxacin for pharmacokinetic purposes in bioequivalence and / or bioavailability studies.

2. METHODOLOGY

The current paper describes the HPLC separation and method validation of two fluorquinolones. Ciprofloxacin, the drug under investigation with a chemical name [[2S-[2a,5a,6β(S*)]]-6-[[Amino(4-hydroxyphenyl)acetyl]amino]-3,3-dimethyl-7-oxo-4-thia-1-azabicyclo[3.2.0]heptane-2-carboxylic acid] has a molecular formula of $C_{16}H_{19}N_3O_5S \cdot 3H_2O$ and a molecular weight of 419.45. Gatifluoxacin with a chemical name of 7-[(R)-2-amino-2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)acetamido]-3-methyl-3-phenyl-4-carboxylic acid monohydrate is used as an internal standard. Its molecular formula and molecular weight are $C_{16}H_{17}N_3O_5S \cdot H_2O$ and 381.40 respectively.

2.1 Standards and Reagents

Ciprofloxacin standard and Gatifluoxacin internal standard were kindly provided by Shaphaco, pharmaceutical Industry, Yemen. Acetonitrile, methanol HPLC grade and phosphoric acid were purchased from ACROS, U.S.A), while analytical grade ethyl acetate was obtained from Merck, Germany. Analytical grade potassium hydrogen phosphate di-basic was from Fisher, U.K. All other reagents were of an analytical grade. Blank plasma was obtained a local plasma bank.

2.2 Instrumentations and Chromatographic Conditions:

Before analysis, all samples were vortexed using SpinMix Gallenkamp mixer and then centrifuged at a speed of 4000 rpm/min using Centrifuge model 800 made in China. Waters HPLC system (Waters, USA) equipped with 1515 isocratic pump and 2487 dual wavelength UV-Vis detector was used for analysis. The detector was set at 279 nm to monitor the drug and the internal standard. The separation was achieved using waters symmetry C18, 5 μ m (150 \times 3.9 mm) HPLC column. The column flow rate was set to 1.3 ml/min. Three times of the 20 μ l loop volume was injected each time. Drug and internal standard data were acquired and processed using Breeze's software running on Windows XP professional. The HPLC mobile phase was made by preparing a mixture of 72 % phosphat buffer (pH = 3.1) with 12 % Acetonitrile and 16% methanol. An ion pair reagent, tetrabutyleammonium hydroxide (12ml/L), was added to the mobile phase to minimize peak tailing. The buffer was prepared by taking the appropriate amount of potassium hydrogen phosphate dibasic and placing it in 1 L to make a final concentration of 20 mM. The pH of the buffer was adjusted to 3.1 using phosphoric acid and NaOH and was measured with Hanna membrane pH meter model HI 8314 made in Romania. The mobile phase was filtered under vacuum through 0.45 μ m pores aqueous Millipore filter membrane.

2.3 Preparation of calibration curve and volunteers' samples:

The preparation of 1 mg/ml Ciprofloxacin stock solution in 5% acetonitrile with de-ionized water was done first by placing 50 mg Ciprofloxacin in 50 ml volumetric flask and adding the solvent with sonication until complete dissolution. The working solution of 50 μ g/ml was prepared from the stock solution in a 5% acetonitrile as well. Gatifluoxacin internal standard with a concentration of 200 μ g/ml was prepared in a mixture of acetic acid, buffer (pH 3.1) and methanol (1:54:45, v/v/v). Calibration curve standards, were first prepared by taking 0, 200, 400, 1200, 2000, 2800 and 4000 μ l Ciprofloxacin working solution (50 μ g/ml) and placing each pipetted volume in a separate 10 ml volumetric flask. To each volumetric flask, 1000 μ l of 200 μ g/ml Gatifluoxacin was added, then the volume was completed with blank plasma to 10 ml. From each solution, 200 μ l was taken and placed in a new clean Eppendorf tube. Then, 200 μ l of 10% perchloric acid was added to the tube. This gave final calibration curve standard concentrations of 0, 0.5, 1, 3, 7 and 10 μ l Ciprofloxacin and 10 μ l Gatifluoxacin. Each tube was closed well, vortexed and centrifuged for 15 min. The supernatant was then transferred into another new clean Eppendorf tube. 60 μ l of this supernatant was injected in the HPLC 20 μ l injection loop to make sure that no sample dilution was taken place in the injection loop. Ciprofloxacin and Gatifluoxacin with concentrations of

7 µg/ml and 10 µg/ml respectively were prepared separately and treated in a similar way as described for calibration curve standards. 60 µl of the supernatant of each was injected in the HPLC 20µl injection loop. The three concentrations; 1, 3 and 7 µg/ml. of calibration curve plasma solutions were used as low, medium and high quality control injections, respectively. Volunteers' blood samples were collected at different time intervals, before (zero time) and 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12, 16 and 24 hours following oral administration of one 500 mg either test or reference Ciprofloxacin tablet to each of the volunteers according to randomization scheme. Blood samples were put into lithium heparin tubes, directly centrifuged and the supernatant plasma transferred into other pre-labeled tubes and stored at -20 °C until sample preparation. To prepare volunteers' plasma for injection, 200 µl of the plasma was taken, and placed in a new clean Eppendorf tube, to which 20 µl of 200 µg/ml Gatifluoxacin internal standard and 180 µl of 10% percholoric acid were added. The content of the tube was then treated as described for standard samples.

2.4- Method Validation:

Method validation was studied according to the current international approach regarding the bio-analytical method validation, which satisfied the requirements of most of applicable statutes and regulations (FDA 2000; FDA 1994; ICH 1994; FDA 2001 and ICH 1996) Accordingly, the method validation was evaluated in terms of selectivity, linearity, accuracy, precession recovery and sensitivity and stability. The method linearity for Ciprofloxacin determination in human plasma was confirmed for a range of concentrations from 0.5 – 10 µg/ml. Standard calibration curves of 6 points were prepared and analyzed. In each day of the validation course, a calibration curve was prepared and its goodness of fit was calculated by linear regression equation ($y = bx + a$) of the best-fit peak area ratios versus concentration, where b , a and y respectively represented slop, intercept and the peak areas ratios of Ciprofloxacin to that of the internal standard and x represents the concentration (µg/ml). Six out of seven non-zero standards including lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) and upper limit of quantification (ULOQ), should deviate by more than 20% and 15% respectively.

In addition, the coefficient of correlation should be consistently greater than or equal to 0.999 during the course of validation. The specificity of the method was determined by screening six different batches of controlled human blank plasma and was verified by the absence of any co-eluted peak of endogenous plasma components at the retention times of the drug and the internal standard. Intra-and inter-day accuracy and precision were determined using three different concentrations in human plasma QCs (1, 3 and 7 µg/mL), with 5 replicates being used per concentration. The deviation of the mean from the nominal value served as the measure of accuracy. The accuracy and precision deviation values should be within 15% of the nominal values except at LLOQ where it shouldn't deviate by more than 20%. For inter-day calculations, the analysis of QCs was repeated on 3 separate days to permit assessments of accuracy and precision.

To calculate the method recovery, the detector response obtained from the injections of the prepared QC samples were compared to the detector response of an equivalent pure authentic standard solution that was prepared to contain a drug and internal standard concentration assuming 100% recovery. The absolute recoveries were calculated for both Ciprofloxacin and internal standard at three concentration levels (1, 3 and 7 µg/mL) by comparing the relevant peak areas of the extracted samples with the peak areas of an equivalent un-extracted pure authentic standard solution. The lowest standard concentration in the calibration curve was considered as the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) and should be identifiable, discrete and reproducible with precision \leq 20% and accuracy of 80-120%. Ciprofloxacin and Ciprofloxacin stability under the current conditions were also evaluated using five QC samples for each time interval session, at both the low and the high QC samples. Twenty QC samples at each concentration of two different levels were allocated to carry out the short-term stability. Five QC samples at each level were analyzed for initial concentration determination at zero time. Five QC samples at each level were left on the bench top at room temperature for 24 hours and at -20 °C for 14 days then analyzed. Stability was calculated by comparing tested samples analyzed after 24 and 14 days time interval with those analyzed initially.

3. Results and Discussions:

The validation results of the developed method are evaluated according to the following criteria:

3.1. Linearity

The calibration/standard curve of the method is constructed and found to have a linear relationship in the range of 0.5 to 10 µg/ml between peak area ratio of Ciprofloxacin / Ciprofloxacin and analyte concentration with regression coefficient value (r^2) equals to 0.9998. The slop and intercept of the calibration curve are found to be 0.295 and 0.0353 respectively. These values are calculated based on the average of 6 measurements for each point used to construct the calibration curve.

3.2. Specificity/ selectivity

The specificity of the method is determined by comparing the chromatograms obtained from the samples containing Ciprofloxacin and internal standard Gatifluoxacin with those obtained from blank samples. Figure 1a shows a chromatogram for a blank plasma sample containing 10 µg/ml Gatifluoxacin indicating the method specificity. As shown in the Figure, the internal standard is well resolved from the blank peak. Figure 1b shows HPLC analysis of low, QC Ciprofloxacin with IS. The two compounds are well resolved from each other and from the plasma peak as well. The method is applied to the analysis of volunteers' plasma sample. Ciprofloxacin in the volunteers' samples start to appear after 30 min of drug administration (data is not shown), however, maximum concentration of Ciprofloxacin appears after 2 hours of administration as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure (1a): HPLC chromatogram showing 10µg/ml Gatifloxacin alone in human plasma (chromatographic conditions are described in section 2.2)

Figure (1b): HPLC chromatogram showing low QC 1µg/ml Ciprofloxacin and 10µg/ml (Gatifluoxacin) in human plasma (chromatographic conditions are described in section 2.2)

Figure (2): HPLC chromatogram showing Volunteer human plasma sample after 120 minutes following administration of test product (Ciproxone[®] 500mg capsule). Chromatographic conditions are described in section 2.2.

3.3. Accuracy and Precision

Method accuracy and precision are determined from intra-day and inter-day values for Ciprofloxacin in human plasma as defined above. The % coefficient of variance (%CV) for intra-day accuracy range from 0.24-2.47%. The accuracy of intra-day data ranged from -0.44 to 3.51%. The between-day accuracy for low, medium and high QCs Ciprofloxacin are found to be 6.53, 0.05 and 0.15% respectively while % CV of low, medium and high QCs are respectively 0.85, 0.14 and 0.10%. These results are within the acceptable range and suggest that the method is reproducible and accurate.

3.4. Recovery

The % recovery of low, medium and high QC Ciprofloxacin in plasma and mobile (n = 5) as well as the recovery of Gatifloxacin internal standard are calculated and shown in Tables 1 and 2. These data indicate that the precipitation of plasma protein with perchloric acid is sufficient enough to ensure a high extraction recovery of Ciprofloxacin and Gatifloxacin from plasma that fulfills the method validation guidelines.

Table 1: Analytical recovery data of Ciprofloxacin in mobile phase and human plasma.

Replicates No.	In mobile phase $\mu\text{g/ml}$			In plasma $\mu\text{g/ml}$		
	1	3	7	1	3	7
1	0.96	2.88	7.05	1.18	2.91	6.93
2	1.10	2.99	6.98	0.96	3.09	6.95
3	0.90	3.04	6.80	0.98	3.01	7.01
4	0.98	3.00	6.89	1.08	3.05	7.01
5	0.93	2.95	7.02	1.06	2.97	7.06
Mean	0.974	2.97	6.95	1.05	3.01	6.99
SD	0.077	0.061	0.10	0.09	0.07	0.05
CV%	7.905	2.07	1.47	1.68	0.46	0.15
Recovery%	97.40	99.07	99.25	105.22	100.20	99.97

Table 2: Analytical recovery data of internal standard Gatifloxacin in mobile phase and plasma.

Replicates No.	In mobile phase $10\mu\text{g/ml}$	In plasma $10\mu\text{g/ml}$
1	9.96	9.90
2	9.87	10.00
3	9.98	9.88
4	10.03	9.95
5	9.99	9.98
Mean	9.94	9.97
SD	0.05	0.06
CV%	0.46	0.59
Recovery%	99.42	99.66

3.5. Sensitivity:

The method sensitivity was evaluated in term of LOD and LLOQ. The LOD was determined by using the signal-to-noise ratio of 3:1 and comparing test results from samples with known concentrations of analyte against blank samples. Using the developed method, LOD is calculated to $0.0090 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) for Ciprofloxacin is $0.032 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in plasma. The value of LLOQ is a higher than that reported (Gonzalez et al 2006) in which they used fluoremetric detection but it is better than the values reported by other groups (Maya et al 2001 and Neckel et al 2002) using the **same detection method**.

3.6. Stability

Stability data for Ciprofloxacin plasma samples at low and high QC samples are given below in Tables 3 and 4. The data show that the Ciprofloxacin concentrations after 24 hour storage at room temperature (short term stability) are within the acceptable range compared to the initial concentrations. Similarly, calculated concentrations of low and high QCs Ciprofloxacin after 14 days of storage at -20°C are also within the permissible values.

Table 3: Stability data for Ciprofloxacin plasma samples at low and high QC samples after 24 hours at room temperature of preparation

Replicate No.	QC Low (1 µg/ml)		QC High (7 µg/ml)	
	Initial	After 24 hrs	Initial	After 24 hrs
1	1.03	0.72	7.19	6.95
2	0.82	1.00	7.07	7.06
3	0.90	1.03	7.03	7.02
4	0.97	0.99	7.07	6.99
5	1.08	1.02	7.06	6.70
Mean	0.96	0.95	7.09	6.94
SD	0.10	0.13	0.06	0.14
CV%	2.17	2.78	0.18	0.41
Stability	96.00 %	95.00%	101.30%	99.14%

Table (4): Stability data at -20°C for Ciprofloxacin plasma samples at low and high QC samples after 14 days of preparation

Replicate No.	QC Low (1 µg/ml)		QC High (7 µg/ml)	
	Initial	After 14 days	Initial	After 14 days
1	1.03	1.03	7.19	7.19
2	0.82	0.82	7.07	7.07
3	0.90	0.90	7.03	7.03
4	0.97	0.97	7.07	7.07
5	1.08	0.99	7.06	6.93
Mean	0.96	0.94	7.09	7.06
SD	0.10	0.08	0.06	0.09
CV%	2.17	1.79	0.18	0.26
Stability	96.00 %	94.00%	101.00%	100.00%

Conclusions

The present study showed a good sensitivity and specificity for the determination of the Ciprofloxacin in human plasma. Ciprofloxacin and Gatifluoxacin eluted about 4.2 and 8.4 min, respectively at a flow rate of 1.3 ml/min. The mean recovery of Ciprofloxacin in plasma for low, medium and high QCs (1, 3 and 7 µg/ml) were 105.22, 100.20 and 99.97% respectively while Ciprofloxacin recovery in mobile were 97.40, 99.07 and 99.25% respectively. The recovery of the internal standard Gatifluoxacin at a concentration of 10 µg/ml in the plasma and the mobile phase were 99.66% and 99.42% respectively. The assay showed excellent relationships between peak area ratios and plasma concentrations ($r^2 \geq 0.9998$). The limit of detection was 0.0090 µg/ml, and the limit of quantification was 0.032 µg/ml of plasma. The developed method of analysis provided a sensitive and specific assay for Ciprofloxacin in human plasma. It was shown that this method was suitable for the analysis of Ciprofloxacin in the human plasma samples.

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